

Polymerisation of Some Unsaturated Fatty Acids.

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Polymerisation of simpler unsaturated acids such as acrylic acid, has been studied by Staudinger and others (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1929, **12**, 1107; *Ber.*, 1931, **64**, 2091; Pechmann and Rohm, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 427; Linnemann, *Annalen*, 1872, **163**, 369), who found that light has a powerful polymerising effect, while polymerisation of the methyl ester of crotonic acid has been studied by Pechmann (*Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 3323). Polymerisation of oleic acid and its methyl ester has been effected by Eichwald (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1922, **35**, 505) by means of silent electric discharge with the production of highly viscous products whose composition, however, remains unknown. The methyl ester of linolic acid had been polymerised by Kino (*Sci. papers of Inst. Phys. Chem Res. Tokyo*, 1933, **20**, 103) while ricinoleic acid has been polymerised by Grün (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **31**, 505) with the production of a solid rubber-like mass.

In the present investigation polymerisation of oleic and other unsaturated acids has been effected with the help of stannic chloride as a catalyst and highly viscous polymers have thus been obtained. These polymers, when decarboxylated, yielded lubricating oils similar to those obtained from petroleum.

Method of Polymerisation.

In a new Nessler's tube, provided with a mechanical stirrer, a definite quantity of oleic acid was taken and to this a known volume of stannic chloride was added, when considerable evolution of heat took place. The reaction was carried out at 100° in an oil-bath for 10 hours in an atmosphere of dry carbon dioxide. Evolution of hydrochloric acid gas was considerable in the beginning but towards the end it decreased. The product was then extracted with petroleum ether and washed thoroughly with water acidulated with hydrochloric acid until ash-free and was then washed free from all traces of the acid.

The ethereal solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and petroleum ether was then evaporated off completely under reduced pressure below 60°. To prevent back-rush it was found necessary to introduce a "T" piece connection between the evaporating apparatus and the suction, one end being connected to atmospheric air through a wash-bottle containing sulphuric acid.

Progress of polymerisation was observed by noting the changes of the physical constants.

TABLE I.

Progress of polymerisation with stannic chloride at 100°.

	Oleic acid.	Polymerised product with catalyst	
		5% by vol. (sample A.)	20% by vol. (sample B)
Sp. gr. at 28°	0.890	0.914	0.936
n_{28}°	1.448	1.452	1.462
Refractive const.	0.3006	0.2951	0.2936
η_{28}°	36.8E1	153.1E1	...
M. W. (cryoscopic)	280	553	1610
Iodine value (Hanus)	88.9	47.55	27.7
Acid value	198.6	150.3	124.1
Acid value (by heating with alcoholic potash)	...	151.4	124.8

Results in Table I show that the amount of stannic chloride added has a considerable influence on the degree of polymerisation of oleic acid. Its action is, therefore, not strictly catalytic. Evolution of heat during the polymerisation suggests the formation of intermediate compound of the unsaturated acid with stannic chloride. Stable compounds of stannic chloride with aromatic acids and with aliphatic dicarboxylic acids have been obtained by Hieber (*Annalen*, 1924, **439**, 97). The instability of these compounds activates the molecule and causes polymerisation. The decomposition of the intermediate compound with evolution of carbon dioxide indicates the carboxyl group being involved in the reaction with stannic chloride. Partial decarboxylation of the extremely stable fatty acids at a temperature not above 100° is rather significant. This decarboxylation

is further borne out by the fact that the polymer has a lower acid value than the theoretical.

Examination of Polymerised Product.

The product obtained by polymerisation of oleic acid was evidently a mixture of different polymer homologues, dissolved in one another.

Attempts were made to separate the various constituents by vacuum distillation. A solid or semisolid product distilled over at 210°-220°/6mm. and was found to be a mixture of stearic and oleic acids, while the residue was a highly viscous tarry product. In view of the large yield of stearic acid and its presence not being satisfactorily accounted for, the original oleic acid was subjected to a similar vacuum distillation but no solid stearic acid could be obtained. It was thus evident that stearic acid had been formed during the process of polymerisation of oleic acid. The quantity of the stearic acid (77.6%) in the mixture was calculated from iodine value of the distillate which consisted of oleic and stearic acids only. The experimental results are given below.

TABLE II.

Distillation of polymerised product.

	Polymerised oleic acid	Distillate at 210-20°.	Distillate at 220-25°.	Residue.
Iodine value (Hanus)	27.7	20.2	44.7	61.8
Acid value	124.1	124.1	145.5	130.2
M. W. (cryoscopic)	1610	306.5	...	750.3
Consistency	Semi-solid	Solid	Liquid	Tarry viscous
Yield	21.3 g.	5.6 g.	4.8 g.	7.3 g.

The physical and chemical properties of the residue indicate that considerable cracking had taken place and the molecular weight, acid value and other properties had been much affected by the heat to which it had been subjected during distillation.

The presence of stearic acid in the polymer might be attributed to the cracking of the polymer, resulting in the formation of new substances during distillation. The original polymerised product was, therefore, slightly cooled and then centrifuged and the solid, thus obtained, was found identical with stearic acid. The presence of stearic acid, therefore, could not be attributed to cracking, it must have been formed during polymerisation.

Molecular weight.—The rise in molecular weight of the polymerised product was determined by means of the cryoscopic method on the assumption that the Van't Hoff equation applied to dilute solutions of these high molecular substances. It will be seen from Table I that the highest average mol. wt. was 1610, obtained by treatment of oleic acid with 20% SnCl₄ (by volume) for a period of 10 hours. As this product is mixed with considerable amount of oleic and stearic acids, it is evident that the polymer is actually of a much higher order than that indicated by molecular weight determination.

Attempts were also made to determine the molecular weight from the specific viscosity on the assumption that the polymer was a long chain compound of the following type,

and hence the Staudinger formula $\eta_{sp}/C = K_m \cdot M$ was applicable. The K_m constant (29×10^{-4}) was determined with the help of the specific viscosity of pure oleic acid. The molecular weight of sample II (Table III) was found to be 448 (carbon tetrachloride) and 875 (benzene) by the Staudinger's method, while the mol. wt. by cryoscopic method was 1610. The Staudinger formula, which is applicable only to long fibre molecules, is not evidently applicable to this case.

Determination of physical properties.—The physical properties change in a regular manner with rise in molecular weight and hence with the degree of polymerisation. Changes in viscosity (η), refractive index (n), density (d) and iodine value may, therefore, be taken as indications of the degree of polymerisation. The relationship between molecular weight and physical and chemical constants will be evident from Table III.

Relation between M. W. and physical and chemical constants.

Time of reaction = 10 hours.

No. of sample.	Catalyst used.	Temp. of reaction.	M.W.	d_{20}^{20}	n_D^{20}	Refractive constant.	η_{25}^{25}	η_{50}^{50}	Iodine value.	Acid value.
1	ZnCl ₂	22-23°	1.4513	...	45.90° E1	30.95°	63.14 Wj	196.88
2	"	100	1029	0.9391	1.4560	0.2919	122.95	70.08	32.72	153.16
3	AlCl ₃	26-27	610	0.9118	1.4524	0.2960	57.29	37.03	52.28	187.55
4	"	100	1.4532	...	71.36	44.71	50.00	179.94
5	SnCl ₄	26-27	1.4515	...	53.73	36.66	54.40	192.46
6	"	100	1220	0.9481	1.4578	0.2897	285.11	142.85	19.48	138.95
7	SbCl ₃	22-23	1.4506	...	41.36	28.76	65.30	199.98
8	"	100	770	0.9189	1.4538	0.2946	72.83	45.59	46.00	177.63
9	BiCl ₃	22-23	1.4502	...	35.87	25.31	67.92	200.31
10	"	100	799	0.9216	1.4541	0.2939	113.43	65.76	37.62	169.02
11	SnCl ₄	100	1610	27.7	124.1
Oleic acid	280	0.8871	1.4493	0.3027	34.63	24.44	80.00	201.76

Viscosity.—Relative viscosity has been determined by means of the Ostwald apparatus and is given in Engler units. It will be noticed that the viscosity rises with rise in molecular weight. In the region of lower molecular weights, the rise in viscosity is rather slow but in the case of larger molecules, a small increase in the molecular weight causes a considerable increase in the viscosity. This is evidently due to a few large molecules retarding the free flow of other molecules and thus causing abnormal increase in internal friction.

The rise in viscosity may be due to various causes, such as (i) size of molecules, (ii) solvation of the products, and (iii) association of comparatively small mols. as known in soap solutions. In the present instance, however, the latter two causes may be eliminated, as the molecular weight of the polymer remains unchanged in different solvents. Moreover, hydrocarbons obtained by decarboxylation of the polymer have also been found to consist of very large molecules and association of such homo-polar hydrocarbons is extremely unlikely. It may, therefore, be taken that the rise in viscosity correctly indicates the formation of high molecular polymers formed by the union of main valency and not by mere association. No quantitative expression relating viscosity to molecular weight could, however, be obtained.

Density.—Table III shows that density rises with polymerisation. This fact may be attributed to chemical union, for two or more molecules when combined by chemical valency would evidently require less space than the same number of monomer either free or associated in a loose manner.

Iodine value.—All the previous workers on polymerisation have taken the diminution in iodine value as proportional to increase in molecular weight. None of them have, however, taken into account the formation of saturated compounds (such as stearic acid in the present instance). The curve in Fig. 1 shows that with initial small rises in molecular weight, iodine value falls considerably but with subsequent large increase of the molecular weight slight diminution in iodine value takes place. This behaviour may be due to the very small initial concentration of stearic acid in the beginning having very slight influence on the iodine value but with the gradual accumulation of stearic acid iodine value data are affected considerably and in the region of high molecular weights the fall in iodine value is not thus proportional to the rise in molecular weight. A further reason why iodine value cannot be taken as a quantitative test for the progress of polymerisation

is that in this case the carboxyl group might be attached to the double bond or that decarboxylation during polymerisation may cause union to take place at other places than the double bond. Such decarboxylation has actually been observed to take place in this case indicating that union may take place at the centres occupied by carboxyl groups.

FIG. 1

Acid value.—Should the polymerisation take place at the double bond, the product should not change in acid value but it will be seen from Table I that the acid value progressively diminishes as polymerisation advances. This may be due to either of the following reasons:—

- (i) Decarboxylation during polymerisation.
- (ii) Weakness of the carboxyl groups in the polymerised product, the weakness increasing with the degree of polymerisation.
- (iii) Linking of the carboxyl groups at the double bond to form intermolecular or intramolecular anhydrides.

The reasons for this reduction in acid value were carefully sought for. It was found that potentiometric titrations gave identical data as obtained by ordinary titrations. The anhydride formation may also be excluded, as the acid value did not change by heating the substance with alcoholic KOH and then titrating the excess of alkali. Evolution of carbon dioxide was, however, found to take place during polymerisation as has already been mentioned. This is evidently the reason for reduced acid value of the polymerised product as well as of the distillates obtained from the polymerised product.

Influence of Carboxyl Group on Polymerisation.

In order to see if the free carboxyl group has any effect on the course of polymerisation, the methyl ester of oleic acid was prepared and polymerised in the usual manner. It was found that changes in the different physical and chemical constants were very small indicating a rather slow progress in polymerisation. In this case protection of the carboxyl groups prevents decarboxylation and consequently polymerisation is here almost entirely caused by the double bond.

The same result was obtained from the glyceride, olive oil, which contained about 85% of unsaturated glycerides. Here also the polymerisation was very much slower as in the case of the methyl ester. It is, therefore, evident that carboxyl group exercises a profound influence on the course of polymerisation.

TABLE IV.

Polymerisation of methyl ester of oleic acid.

Time = 10 hours. Temp. = room temp. and 100°.

	Original substance.	Product 5% at 26°.	Product polymerised with catalyst 5% at 100°.	Product polymerised with catalyst 15% at 100°.
Sp. gr. at 28°.	0.871	0.877	0.894	0.897
n_{28}°	1.4410	1.4445	1.4485	1.4506
Refractive const.	0.8031	0.8031	0.2997	0.2997
Iodine value (Hanus)	81	81	61.7	58
η_{28}°	7.4 EI	8.1 EI	19 EI	25.8 EI

TABLE V.

Polymerisation of olive oil.

Time = 10 hours. Temp. = room temp. and 100°.

	Olive oil.	Product polymerised with catalyst		
		5% at 26°. 5% at 100°.	15% at 100°.	15% at 100°.
Sp. gr. at 28°.	0.913	0.923	0.925	0.946
n_{28}°	1.4600	1.462	1.4622	1.4635
Refractive const.	0.2993	0.2978	0.2975	0.2915
η_{28}°	68.9 EI	97.2 EI	107.4 EI	125 EI
Iodine value (Hanus)	82.8	76.2	75.7	62.8

Mechanism of Polymerisation.

An attempt to explain the mechanism of polymerisation should take into consideration (a) the formation of saturated stearic acid, (b) evolution of carbon dioxide, (c) lowering of the acid value, (d) the difference in the behaviour of the free acid and its ester, and (e) the large amount of stannic chloride necessary for satisfactory polymerisation. The polymerisation of oleic acid may evidently take place by

(i) Combination of a double bond with a double bond in any of the following manners:

(ii) Combination of carboxyl group with another carboxyl group to form acid anhydrides. (iii) Combination of carboxyl group with a double bond of the same molecule or of another molecule. (iv) Elimination of carboxyl group with evolution of carbon dioxide and hydrogen and combination at the active spot thus originated.

In the experimental results, no evidence of the formation of anhydrides could be obtained, nor could the formation of saturated tetracarboxylic ring compounds (C) in the polymerised product or its distillates be traced. The reactions i (A), i (B) or reaction (iv) must, therefore, be responsible for the polymerisation of oleic acid. For reaction (iv), stannic chloride is necessary to form an intermediate compound similar to those formed with aromatic mono-carboxylic or aliphatic di-carboxylic acids (*loc. cit.*). Such intermediate compounds are decomposed with the evolution of carbon dioxide and hydrogen which reduces stannic to stannous chloride with evolution of hydrochloric acid and also reduces oleic to stearic acid. The stannous chloride formed is not in a position to unite with further molecules of oleic acid and hence a substantial quantity of stannic chloride has to be added to effect polymerisation. The evolution of carbon dioxide is responsible for the lowering of acid value. In the case of the methyl ester such evolution of carbon dioxide from the carboxyl group is prevented which explains the lower degree of polymerisation obtained in the case of the methyl ester and the glyceride of oleic acid.

Polymerisation of linolic acid.—Attempts were then made to polymerise linolic acid which contains a conjugated double bond in addition to the carboxyl group. In this instance the conjugated bond was found to be much more active and here carboxyl group played subsidiary part. The acid value, therefore, remained practically constant though the iodine value fell quickly and viscosity rose with the degree of polymerisation. Molecular weight determination of the final products showed that the degree of polymerisation was very high and several molecules combined to form the polymerised product, which was separated from stannic chloride by extraction with ether instead of petroleum ether.

TABLE VI.

Polymerisation of linolic acid.

Catalyst = stannic chloride. Time = 10 hours. Temp. = Room temp. and 100°.

	Linolic acid.	Linolic acid treated without catalyst	Product polymerised with catalyst		
			5% at 27°	15% at 100°.	20% at 100°.
Sp. gr. at 28°.	0.906	0.910	0.943	0.975	0.984
n_{28}°	1.4615	1.463	1.4815	1.4885	1.4915
Refractive const.	0.3030	0.3029	0.3021	0.2954	0.2944
η_{50}°	15.2 El	23.8 El	15.7 El
Acid value	207.8	207.9	205	202	209
Iodine value (Hanus)	182.5	155.2	108.6	50.2	45.6
M. W. (cryoscopic)	277	317	456	1544	1782

The possibilities of reactions are as follows:

In this case an eight membered as well as a four membered ring may be formed by the union of two molecules while an indefinite number of molecules may also combine together to form an open chain. As increasing molecular weight together with increase in viscosity is obtained, it would appear that bimolecular reaction must play only a minor part and that reaction (III) is mainly responsible for the formation of polymerised product.

Polymerisation of ricinoleic acid.—It would, therefore, be interesting to see how ricinoleic acid containing three reactive groups—one double bond, one hydroxyl group and one carboxyl group—behaves in the course of polymerisation. It will be found from the following table of experimental results that here the iodine value remains practically constant except when 20% or more stannic chloride are added. The polymerised product has the same acid value as the original product. The acetyl value, however, falls quickly. This would show that in this case double bond does not take part in the polymerisation but the hydroxyl group quickly disappears with the formation of an ether or ester type of compound. These esters are, however, very easily saponifiable and hence give the acid value of the original material. If ether formation were the only reaction, a bimolecular compound with a maximum molecular weight of 578 could be formed. But considerably higher molecular weight (*i. e.* 1836) has been found showing that at least six ricinoleic acid molecules are combined to form esters in the following manner:—

TABLE VII.

Polymerisation of ricinoleic acid.

Catalyst = stannic chloride. Time = 10 hrs. Temp. = Room temp. and 100°.

	Ricinoleic acid (original)	Polymerised product with catalyst			
		5% at 28°.	5% at 100°.	15% at 100°.	20% at 100°.
Sp. gr. at 28°.	0.9357	0.9376	0.9387	0.9625	...
n_{28}°	1.4625	1.463	1.465	1.482	1.492
Refractive const.	0.2940	0.2939	0.2947	0.2956	...
Iodine value (Hanus)	88.1	88.6	88.1	89.5	52
Acid value	} at room temp. 130 } on heating 184.1	130	133	184	179
		186.1	185.2	184.1	183.5
Acetyl value (Lewkowitsch method)	141	142	20	6	4.5
η_{28}°	201 EI	215 EI	379 EI
M. W. (cryoscopic method)	675	1836

Decarboxylation of polymerised products.—The polymerised products, obtained above, were decarboxylated with the production of highly viscous hydrocarbons similar to lubricating oils obtained from petroleum. This would seem to support the theory that petroleum hydrocarbons were formed from the polymerisation (and depolymerisation) of unsaturated fatty acids followed by decarboxylation. Such artificial lubricating oils are also interesting from an industrial point of view.

Decarboxylation was effected by heating the polymerised products (30 g.) at 365° with zinc dust (25 g.) for 2½ hours. The resulting product was acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with petroleum ether. The fall in acid value of the products indicated the degree of decarboxylation. The constitution of the hydrocarbons prepared under such drastic conditions could not, however, be

followed systematically. Similar products were obtained from the decarboxylation of the polymerised oleic, linolic, ricinoleic acids. These substances had high refractive index, were highly viscous and dark green in colour with a tinge of fluorescence as in natural petroleum. The properties of the polymerised products and hydrocarbons obtained therefrom are given below. Owing to the high viscosity of the products, Ostwald tubes for determining viscosity could not be used.

TABLE VIII.

Polymerised	Colour.	Smell.	Refractive index.	Iodine value.	Acid value.
Oleic acid	Deep yellow	Rancid	1.462	27.7	124.1
Do decarboxylated	Dark green	Similar to lubricating oil	1.513	23.6	7.6
Linoleic acid	Deep yellow	Rancid	1.491	45.6	209
Do decarboxylated	Green	Like lubricating product	1.524	37.7	12.9
Ricinoleic acid	Deep yellow	Rancid	1.486	52.8	177.9
Do decarboxylated	Dark green	Like lubricating oil	1.516	44.6	11.1